

1 **Campylobacter concisus infection in human intestinal epithelial cells.**

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7 We studied infection with an emerging GI pathogen, *Campylobacter concisus* in a cell culture model In
8 conjunction with RNA-sequencing. Cells underwent changes in cellular identity as a direct result of
9 infection with *Campylobacter* with silencing of *Sp6* and *Tbx2* and activation of *Cebpb*. Cells produced
10 *Csf1r* but repressed *Il1r1*. Polarity changes were induced by *Campylobacter concisus* infection, including
11 activation of *Pard3* and *Pard3b*. We describe the biologically significant changes in epigenetic and nuclear
12 function resulting from *Campylobacter* infection in cells of GI tract in culture, including silencing of *Dnmt3b*
13 and *Chd4*.

14 Citations

15 1. Nielsen, H.L., Engberg, J., Ejlersen, T. and Nielsen, H., 2013. Clinical manifestations of
16 *Campylobacter concisus* infection in children. *The Pediatric infectious disease journal*, 32(11),
17 pp.1194-1198.

18 2. Nielsen, H.L., Dalager-Pedersen, M. and Nielsen, H., 2020. High risk of microscopic colitis after
19 *Campylobacter concisus* infection: population-based cohort study. *Gut*, 69(11), pp.1952-1958.

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